

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D4.1 Data Cube Metadata Model

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Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
API	Application Program Interface
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
EVEREST	European Virtual Environment for Research Earth Science Themes
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICT	Information and communications technology
INGV	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
ISMAR	Istituto di Scienze Marine
MEEO	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
REST	Representational state transfer
RO	Research Objects
T2	Terradue
UiO	Universitetet i Oslo
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WMS	Web Map Services

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1 Executive Summary

RELIANCE, short for Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC, aims to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies: i) Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities; ii) data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access; iii) text mining and semantic enrichment services allowing to extract machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research.

This document describes the machine-readable metadata model that we propose for the description of FAIR Data Cubes, as an essential component in the data-cube-centric Research Objects that will be managed in the services offered by RELIANCE, so as to provide support to our communities of researchers. For the development of this metadata model we have first analysed the dataset search services that our communities of researchers use more often, so as to determine which are the main attributes by which datasets can be found and retrieved. We have also analysed existing metadata models that are being used to describe those datasets, as well as those that are being prominently proposed in the context of the EOSC ecosystem, such as those identified for the representation of FAIR Digital Objects in the context of the EOSC Interoperability Framework. As a result, we have created a set of crosswalks among them, made available as an Excel file with a permanent DOI (Corcho, González-Guardia and Garijo, 2021), which may be refined in the future as a result of the Research Object management activities that will be developed in the project. We have also collected a set of competency questions (also known as user stories or usage scenarios) for which our Data Cube metadata model should provide support. Our metadata model will be implemented as an OWL ontology in the following months, as part of the API development, together with its corresponding documentation and examples, and will be published as a FAIR artefact, following Linked Data publishing principles for vocabularies.

2 Introduction and motivation

To motivate the need for this work, we include here a description of three sample scenarios of usage of RELIANCE technology and services, where Data Cubes have a central role as the carriers of the data that is used in the corresponding experiments. These scenarios are adapted from those already proposed as part of the project description.

Scenario 1. Federica is a marine scientist at CNR ISMAR and as part of her work she monitors marine environmental variables following the Marine Strategy Framework Directive¹. In the first quarter of 2020 she has been in lockdown and she is interested to study the unique data acquired during this historical moment by satellites and in situ sensors. She wants to deepen the understanding of the environmental changes on European Coastal Areas due to the absence of anthropogenic impact detected across the pre-pandemic and post-pandemic phase.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/eu-coast-and-marine-policy/marine-strategy-framework-directive/index_en.htm

Figure 1: The Sentinel2A Images compare the Venice Lagoon waters in April 2019 (left) and during the lockdown in April2020 (right). Credits ESA/ Copernicus

Federica will use the RELIANCE services already integrated in EOSC to manage and enhance the FAIR-ness of her research. Federica starts her work by creating a new Research Object that will be continuously enhanced throughout the entire research lifecycle. The Research Object will be the dynamic and logic container where Federica will encapsulate or link her study materials and resources: data, bibliography, codes, algorithms, workflows, results, annotations and communications. The model used for the description of Research Objects and all of its components is described in RELIANCE Deliverable D5.1 (Corcho, González and Palma, 2021).

Let us now focus on the data that will be used in this research. Federica will start the Graphical User Interface that she normally uses to explore and select the relevant in situ and Copernicus data to work with. Without the need for Federica to know how the data is described internally, she will perform several data discovery and access actions on this GUI so as to identify the data sources that are needed for the research, and these will be included as references in the Research Object that she has created. Some typical parameters that will guide this data discovery actions are the variables that she is looking for (salinity, nutrients, temperature, etc.), the area that she is considering (e.g. the Mediterranean Sea, the Venice Lagoon), the depth of the water for which measurements are searched (e.g., 200m), and the period for which she is looking for data (e.g., the period between 2019 and 2020, so as to make the analysis of differences). After the initial selection of data (which may be refined during the research lifecycle), other activities will be done for the processing of the data, the analysis and reporting of results, etc.

Scenario 2. At the University of Oslo, Anne and her department for Climate Change want to perform a similar research from an atmospheric perspective point of view. Similarly, they use Data Cube related technologies to exploit the wealth of Earth Observation data provided by the Copernicus program.

Figure 2 The Sentinel5P images compare NO2 emissions over Europe in April 2019 (left) and during the lockdown in April 2020 (right). Credits ESA/Copernicus

Anne and her team may be using a different user interface to search and access remote sensing data. And at the same time, if the data cubes used by Federica in her research are made available in existing Research Objects following FAIR principles, those data cubes that were already used by Federica may be available in the same way to Anne. In all of these cases, the parameters used for the discovery of relevant data are similar: types of observations (vegetation, snow cover, ice cover, land-use, cloud coverage), geographical area (e.g., Norway, Sweden, Arctic Sea), and time period. These are independent of the internal models and formats that are used to store data in each community and the software that is being used to process such data.

Scenario 3. In parallel, Elisa and her team of GeoHazard researchers at INGV Rome have been already using research objects for four years within the Supersites network where she contributed the take up of this research lifecycle management paradigm worldwide. Elisa can take advantage of continuous Research Object support and ensure that the data descriptions of those Research Objects follow the recommendations of Data Cube representation provided by RELIANCE, enabling her team to share and disseminate information about volcanic and seismic monitoring across worldwide network and with EOSC scientific communities.

Figure 3 The Supersites network. Background World image Credits: ESA/Copernicus

As discussed in the previous three scenarios, **Data Cubes are a key mechanism to enable an accurate representation and an efficient discovery and access to large collections of multi-temporal, multi resolution satellite imagery and in-situ observations.** In RELIANCE, Data Cubes will be treated as first-class resources, aggregated and described in detail, e.g., how it was generated (specification) or used, in a Data Cube-centric research object (as described further in RELIANCE Deliverable D5.1) (Corcho, González and Palma, 2021).

The metadata model used to describe Data Cubes will need to include properties for the identification of the datasets and for their general description (as nearly all metadata models for data assets provide), for their spatial and temporal resolution, for the experiments, expeditions or instruments used to produce the data, etc. They also have to include other particular parameters used to generate the dataset or subset and the link for access. That is, such detailed description of data cubes will enable not only their discovery, but they will be also useful in case that the data is not actually stored but needs to be recreated, accessed and used efficiently, especially in the case of large datasets.

3 Related work: representing Data Cubes in EOSC

3.1 What is a Data Cube in RELIANCE?

As discussed in the previous section, Data Cubes should enable an accurate description and an efficient discovery and access to large collections of geospatial data, with a clear focus on multi-temporal, multi resolution satellite imagery and in-situ observations. This includes Copernicus data as well as other operational Earth Observation (EO) satellite missions, and many different types of observations made in-situ in specific expeditions and experiments.

Data Cubes are especially relevant in the context of long-term science and environmental monitoring applications, where there is a need for simultaneous access to historical, present and future data, and to apply numerical models that generate hundreds of terabytes per day of re-analysis, forecasts and long-term-scenario data products. We expect that this trend that drives users to request long time-series of data will increase even more in the future, in particular regarding the interest on global change assessment and monitoring to support policy makers decisions on atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere, carbon and other biogeochemical cycles safeguard.

3.2 Existing data repositories for Data Cubes

Several tools are available in the state of the art for satisfying the needs (and matching the skills) of the variety of users that were discussed in Section 1. After a series of interviews with user communities and technology providers involved in RELIANCE, the list of tools described in this section was obtained. This list is by no means meant to be exhaustive, but based on the analysis of those interviews and the current practices of our communities of researchers. This catalogue of tools may be expanded in the future as we pursue the adoption of our proposed metadata model for Data Cube description. The provenance of where these tools came from via the interviews is provided here:

- CNR-ISMAR: The SeaDataNet Data Search Engine, the Copernicus Marine Service, the NOAA’s National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI), Pangaea, the Snapshot VRE and the CNR-ISMAR resource catalogue.
- INGV: the EPOS Portal and the European Catalogue of Volcanoes (EUROVOLC), Pangaea, and the INGV data portal.
- UiO: The CMIPv6 data portal.
- Other (coming from technology and content providers in RELIANCE): ADAM, OGC OpenSearch tools and STAC-based tools.

3.2.1 The SeaDataNet Data Search Engine

The SeaDataNet Data Search Engine (<https://cdi.seadatanet.org/search>) is a dataset catalogue

maintained by the SeaDataNet AISBL (started in 2019). This legal entity provides support for a distributed Marine Data Infrastructure for the management of large and diverse sets of data deriving from in situ observations of the seas and oceans. The

search engine is based on the Common Data Index (CDI).

The current data search engine provides access to more than 2.5 million records, including datasets and groups of observations. The exact amount of datasets is not provided explicitly.

Besides a free search textbox, the attributes that can be used to search for datasets and in-situ observations are the following:

- Geographic coverage, either by bounding box or by sea region in the world.
- Specific areas such as Ices areas, Helcom areas, Ospar areas or MSFD areas.
- Temporal coverage and temporal resolution.
- Parameters: air pressure, air temperature, beach litter abundance, etc.
- Point (and country) of contact.
- Data originator (and its country), custodian (and its country) and distributor (and its country).
- Platform type, instrument type and instrument depth.
- Measuring area type (curve, point, surface)
- Water depth.
- Cruise/station name and Cruise Summary Report
- Project name
- Data access restrictions

For a specific dataset², the following attributes are used to describe it (also available in an XML file):

- General description (What): name, version, abstract, discipline, parameter groups, GEMET-INSPIRE themes, data format, data size, dataset creation time.
- Location information (Where): latitude, longitude, coordinate reference system, measuring area type, water depth, depth reference, sea regions, MSFD areas.
- Temporal information (When): start and end date and time.
- Data acquisition information (How): Instrument type, platform type, cruise name, alternative cruise name, cruise start date, station name, alternative station name, station start date.
- Data management information (Who): data originator and data custodian.
- How to get the data: data distributor, database reference, access/ordering of data, access restrictions.
- Quality and provenance: Quality info, lineage.
- CDI-Metadata items, including a record id.

² For example, <https://cdi.seadatanet.org/report/1000008/v0/xml> (based on ISO 19115-2 Metadata)

3.2.2 The Copernicus Marine Service

The Copernicus Marine Service (or Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service - <https://marine.copernicus.eu/>) is the marine component of the EU Copernicus Programme. It provides authoritative information on the state of the Blue (physical), White (sea ice) and Green (biogeochemical) ocean, on a global and regional scale. It covers both satellite and in-situ observations, and for both of these cases it has some observation requirements: for satellite data in general (CMEMS, 2017), for satellite data for polar oceans (Bertino et al., 2016), and for in-situ observations (CMEMS, 2018) in terms of the space and time coverage of the data that can be made available through it.

At the time of writing this report, a total of 180 products are provided in the product/data catalogue of this service: https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/?option=com_csw&task=results

The high-level parameters that can be used to select products/datasets in the data catalogue are:

- Regional domain: Global Ocean, Arctic Ocean, Baltic Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Iberia-Biscay-Ireland Regional Seas, European North-West Shelf Seas
- Temporal coverage
- Product with depth level
- Parameters: temperature, salinity, sea surface height, current velocity, mixed layer thickness, sea ice, wind, plankton, etc.

And the full set of attributes used to describe products/datasets are available as an OGC CSW document³:

- Identifier, overview and references
- Geographical coverage (including the domain area if any)
- Observation/Models
- Product type: forecast, invariant, near-real-time, etc.
- Processing level
- Data assimilation
- Variables (associated to the aforementioned parameters). For example, for temperature we have sea_water_potential_temperature (T), sea_water_potential_temperature_at_sea_floor (bottomT), etc.
- Spatial resolution
- Vertical coverage
- Coordinate reference system
- Feature type (e.g., Grid)
- Temporal coverage (already discussed above) and temporal resolution (hourly-mean, daily-mean, monthly-mean, 6-hourly-instantaneous, etc.)

³ For example,

https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=GLOBAL_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_PHY_001_024

- Update frequency (daily, monthly, etc.)
- Production unit (who created the dataset)
- Original file format (e.g., NetCDF-3)

Finally, there are also references to associated services (OGC WMS, OGC SOS, direct file, etc.).

3.2.3 NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI)

This service (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/>) announces itself as a provider of more than 37 petabytes of comprehensive atmospheric, coastal, oceanic and geophysical data, with the following broad set of categories: Air Temperature and Atmospheric Properties, Arctic and Sea Ice, Ecosystems and Natural Resources, Geomagnetism, Global Climate, Gulf of Mexico, Maps, Marine Geology and Geophysics, Natural Hazards, Disasters and Severe Weather, Ocean Climate, Ocean Exploration and Research, Ocean Profile, Paleoclimatology, Precipitation, Satellite Oceanography, Space Weather, U.S. and Regional Climate.

Two main tools are provided for the discovery of datasets and products: the NOAA OneStop (<https://data.noaa.gov/onestop/>, described as a tool to explore data from across scientific disciplines, formats, time periods, and locations), and the NCEI Data Access (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/search/index>). There are also other tools for developers, including an API (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/support/access-search-service-api-user-documentation>), map services, etc.

Searching via these tools is made as less structured as possible, including textboxes and selectors around What, Where and When, with some more specific selectors (e.g., the name of a station for some climate-related

observations). While the What is based on types of observations (land surface, ocean, radar, satellite), types of datasets, keywords (from the [NASA Global Change Master Directory \(GCMD\) Science and Services Keywords](#)), formats, data types (air temperature, precipitation, etc.), the Where is based on a wide list of areas (with the possibility of considering a bounding box).

As for the metadata available for each dataset⁴, it is structured as follows (following the ISO 19115-2 standard):

- Data Access: pointers to services that allow searching for data, downloads, distribution formats, distributors, and point of contact.
- Time and location
- Documentation, including general documentation, processing documents and associated resources.

⁴ For example, <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.ncdc:C00861>

- General description: publication dates, edition, data presentation form, dataset progress status, data update frequency, purpose, use limitations.
- Credits: citation, authors, principal investigators, collaborators, publishers.
- Keywords: theme keywords, datacenter keywords, place keywords, project keywords, stratum keywords.
- Constraints: on use, access and fees.
- Lineage: processing steps, instrument, platform, etc.

3.2.4 Pangaea

This service (<https://www.pangaea.de/>) is hosted by the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research (AWI) and the Center for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen (MARUM). It is announced as an Open Access library aimed at archiving, publishing and distributing georeferenced data from Earth System research. At the time of writing, it contains around 400K datasets from approximately 500 projects.

The main tool for searching is based on an ElasticSearch engine that provides facets related to: authors, publication year, topics, projects, basis, method/device, campaign, and location. These are the items that are used for the metadata of each dataset. Besides some <https://schema.org/Dataset> metadata

that is applied to all datasets archived in PANGAEA, the following attributes are also provided⁵:

- Citation
- Identifier
- Name
- Abstract
- Keywords
- Coverage (geographical and temporal)
- Size (in case that the dataset is composed of several datasets)

All datasets archived in PANGAEA contain Schema.org/Dataset metadata. It also supports interconnections with data portals such as ICSU World Data System, the World Meteorological Organisation Information System (WIS), the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), OpenAIRE, the Global Biodiversity Facility (GBIF) and the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), the German Federation for Biological Data (GFBio), and the Data Observation Network for Earth (DataONE).

⁵ For example, <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.929564>

- GEMET-INSPIRE themes.
- Categories and keywords.
- Point of contact for the dataset.
- Spatial and temporal extent.
- Publication date.
- Coordinate Reference System.
- Formats in which the resource is available.
- Lineage information, available as a textual resource.
- Contact for the data custodian.

3.2.7 The EPOS Data Access Portal

EPOS (European Plate Observing System) is a European Research Infrastructure that groups together Earth Scientists with other types of stakeholders in the context of what is known as Solid Earth Science. Researchers in this area are focused on understanding the internal structure and dynamics of planet Earth, from the inner core to the surface.

As part of the infrastructure, EPOS maintains several community portals (catalogued in <https://epos-no.uib.no/epos-portals/>) related to different areas of Solid Earth Science: Seismology, Volcano Observations, Near-fault observatories, GNSS data and products, satellite data, geomagnetic observations, anthropogenic hazards, geological

information and modelling, multi-scale laboratories, and geo-energy testbeds for low carbon energy. Besides, there is a data access portal (<https://www.ics-c.epos-eu.org/data/search>) that contains, at the time of writing, 227 products that are organized according to the previous classification of areas.

Search in this data catalogue can be done using a combination of the following search criteria:

- Spatial/geographical bounding box where observations are available
- Temporal coverage.
- Free text keywords (currently 380 keywords), e.g., 3d/4d model, deception island, etc.
- Organisations that produce the data (currently 36 of them)

For each of these resources⁷, the following metadata is maintained:

- Name
- ID
- Description
- Documentation
- Spatial and temporal coverage
- DOI (if available)
- Service and data providers

⁷ For example, <https://volcanoboxws.obsea.es:5000/api/epos/map-metadata/lavaflow/DeceptionIsland>

- Service description
- License
- Endpoint

And specific metadata can be provided by the data providers in each of the cases (for example, in the aforementioned example the following additional metadata is provided: access to the map, additional data, authors, category, date of creation, date of event, functionality, geographical location, volcano details – ID, lat, long, name -, hazard type, reference system, keywords, etc.), as well as specific observations, stations, networks, etc., to access the specific data.

Finally, in general and although not available directly from the EPOS Data Portal, data in EPOS is organized according to four levels:

- Level 0: raw data, or basic data (example: seismograms, accelerograms, SAR images)
- Level 1: data products coming from nearly automated procedures (earthquake locations, magnitudes, focal mechanism, shakemaps)
- Level 2: data products resulting by scientists' investigations (crustal models, strain maps, earthquake source models, etc.)
- Level 3: integrated data products coming from complex analyses or community shared products (hazards maps, catalogue of active faults, etc.)

According to the EPOS ICS-TCS Integration Guidelines⁸, the metadata format to be used in order to support metadata catalogues in this context is CERIF, although this is not evident in the EPOS Data Access portal.

3.2.8 The European Catalogue of Volcanoes and Volcanic Areas (EUROVOLC)

The European Catalogue of Volcanoes and Volcanic Areas (<https://volcanos.eurovolc.eu/>) is one of the main products of EUROVOLC, providing access to data from 47 volcanoes that belong to and/or are monitored by European countries.

This catalogue allows browsing through the existing volcanoes in the catalogue, and obtaining information about them, with a basic search by country, volcanic area, eruption dates, eruption types, maximum Volcanic Explosivity Index (VEI), magnitude, eruption scenario (small, moderate, etc.), eruption location (central volcano, etc.), central volcano type,

existence of external water, column maximum height, magma composition, whether it has an isopach map, and many other observed parameters (tephra mass, tephra volume, tephra DRE, lava volume, bulk volume, bulk deposit DRE volume, etc.). It also allows searching for situations where there were fatalities, evacuations, injuries, etc.

Given a specific volcano (e.g., <https://volcanos.eurovolc.eu/?volcano=SAN#>), a set of specific metadata is provided, grouped in the following groups:

- Smithsonian ID

⁸ EPOS-IP WP6 & WP7 teams, . (2015). EPOS ICS-TCS Integration Guidelines - Handbook for TCS integration: Level-2. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.34666>

- Name and alternative name (normally in the original language of the country where it is located)
- Short description
- Details of the Central Volcano, with approximately 20 parameters.
- Details of the fissure swarm, with approximately 20 parameters.
- A detailed description, in natural language, with 14 descriptors.
- Available map layers

Data citation, when used, is recommended to follow the following example: Larsen, G. & Guðmundsson, M.T. (Last update date). Katla. In: Barsotti, S., Di Vito, M. & Óladóttir, B.A. (eds). European Catalogue of Volcanoes. IMO, UI and CPD-NCIP. Retrieved from <https://volcanos.eurovolc.eu/?volcano=<<ID>>>

3.2.9 The INGV Data Portal

The INGV Data Portal (<https://data.ingv.it/>) contains at the time of writing 179 datasets that are being used by INGV researchers as part of their research. As already described for the SNAPSHOT VRE, in section 3.2.5, this portal is based on the CKAN platform that has been commonly used for open government data sites. As a result, it provides metadata about datasets according to the DCAT-AP application profile, and it also provides the metadata about the dataset catalogue according to schema.org/Dataset.

Given a specific dataset⁹, other metadata

schemas that are being used to expose some of the datasets include:

- CodeMeta for the source code associated to a dataset (e.g., <https://data.crosscite.org/application/vnd.codemeta.ld+json/10.13127/bsi/201701>).
- Citeproc (e.g., <https://data.crosscite.org/application/vnd.citationstyles.csl+json/10.13127/bsi/201701>)
- OAI DataCite (e.g., https://oai.datacite.org/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_datacite&identifier=doi:10.13127/bsi/201701).
- NASA DIF (<https://data.ingv.it/metadata/dif/321>)
- ISO 19115 (<https://data.ingv.it/metadata/iso19115/321>).

3.2.10 The CMIP6 Data Portal

The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is supported by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) and is currently in its sixth phase, with CMIP6 (<https://esgf-node.lnl.gov/projects/cmip6/>). This is a common infrastructure used by the climate research community in order to collect, organize and distribute the output from models that are performing common sets of experiments.

⁹ For example, <https://data.ingv.it/en/dataset/321>

Welcome, Guest. | Login | Create Account

Home Contact Us Data Nodes Status You are at the [ESGF@DOE/LLNL](#) node [Technical Support](#)

MIP Era +

Activity +

Model Cohort +

Product +

Source ID +

Institution ID +

Source Type +

Nominal Resolution +

Experiment ID +

Sub-Experiment +

Variant Label +

Grid Label +

Table ID +

Frequency +

Realm +

WARNING: Not all models include a variant "r1i1p1f1", and across models, identical values of variant_label do not imply identical variants! To learn which forcing datasets were used in each variant, please check modeling group publications and documentation provided through ES-DOC.

CMIP6 project data downloads are unrestricted. Downloads should be performed with the -s option to a wget script without the need to login. When using this method for download, ensure you are not using additional options, eg. -s and -H should never be combined.

Enter Text: Search Reset Display 10 results per page [More Search Options](#)

Show All Replicas Show All Versions Search Local Node Only (Including All Replicas)

Search Constraints: xvegetation cover, arctic

Total Number of Results: 618144
-1- 2 3 4 5 6 Next >>

Please login to add search results to your Data Cart
Expert Users: you may display the search URL and return results as XML or return results as JSON

1. CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr
Data Node: vesg.ipsl.upmc.fr
Version: 20201222
Total Number of Files (for all variables): 1
Full Dataset Services: [Show Metadata](#) | [List Files](#) | [WGET Script](#) | [Show Citation](#) | [PID](#) | [Globus Download](#) | [Further Info](#)
2. CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Lmon.landCoverFrac.gr
Data Node: vesg.ipsl.upmc.fr
Version: 20201222
Total Number of Files (for all variables): 1
Full Dataset Services: [Show Metadata](#) | [List Files](#) | [WGET Script](#) | [Show Citation](#) | [PID](#) | [Globus Download](#) | [Further Info](#)

An up-to-date list of datasets is available at https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/ArchiveStatistics/esgf_data_holdings/, counting at the time of writing almost 5 million datasets. The dataset search engine, available at <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/cmip6/>, provides an advanced faceted search interface for finding those datasets, with the following groups of attributes:

- Activity and product information: the phase of CMIP (currently CMIP6 only), the group of activity (AerChemMIP, C4MIP, CDRMIP, etc.), the model cohort (currently only registered datasets) and the type of product (currently only model outputs).
- Lineage information: the source ID, the institution ID (from 42 institutions currently), the source type and the nominal resolution in kilometres or degrees (10 km, 100 km, 10000 km, 1x1 degree, etc.).
- Experiment information: experiment ID, subexperiment, variant label and grid label.
- Other types of information, such as the table ID, frequency, realm, variables and the CF standard names used in the experiments.
- The data node where the data is archived.

All these combinations of attributes, together with a free text search and a temporal window search, allow for looking for all the data whose metadata is stored in this portal.

Once a dataset is obtained¹⁰, several options exist in order to get details about its metadata, list the files that it is composed of, download them via HTTP, GridFTP, OpenDAP, Globus, etc., show the citation to the dataset or get its PID. Dataset metadata follows the NetCDF format, and contains the following attributes (we include the attributes of the ones associated to the example selected, as a summary), among others:

- General information
 - o id = CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr.v20201222|vesg.ipsl.upmc.fr
 - o dataset_id_template = %(mip_era)s.%(activity_drs)s.%(institution_id)s.%(source_id)s.%(experiment_id)s.%(member_id)s.%(table_id)s.%(variable_id)s.%(grid_label)s

¹⁰ For example, the one that may be found using the following ID: CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr

- master_id = CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr
- instance_id = CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr.v20201222
- version = 20201222
- _timestamp = 2021-02-23T08:31:15.165Z
- citation_url = <http://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/meta/CMIP6/CMIP6.PAMIP.IPSL.IPSL-CM6A-LR.pdSST-futArcSIC.r100i1p1f1.Emon.nwdFracLut.gr.v20201222.json>
- pid = hdl:21.14100/ac2ee022-646a-3e35-950c-717781212867
- data_specs_version = 01.00.28
- retracted = false
- Activity and product information
 - mip_era = CMIP6
 - model_cohort = Registered
 - activity_drs = PAMIP
 - activity_id = PAMIP
 - product = model-output
 - project = CMIP6
- Lineage information
 - source_id = IPSL-CM6A-LR
 - institution_id = IPSL
 - source_type = AGCM
 - member_id = r100i1p1f1
 - nominal_resolution = 250 km
- Experiment information
 - experiment_id = pdSST-futArcSIC
 - experiment_title = Atmosphere time slice with present day SST and future Arctic SIC
 - variant_label = r100i1p1f1
 - grid = LMDZ grid
 - grid_label = gr
- Other types of information
 - table_id = Emon
 - frequency = mon
 - realm = land
 - variable = nwdFracLut
 - variable_id = nwdFracLut
 - variable_long_name = Non-woody Vegetation Percentage Cover
 - variable_units = %
 - cf_standard_name = area_fraction
- Data node and access information
 - access = HTTPServer, GridFTP, OPENDAP, Globus
 - data_node = vesg.ipsl.upmc.fr
 - directory_format_template =
 %(root)s/%(mip_era)s/%(activity_drs)s/%(institution_id)s/%(source_id)s/%(experiment_id)s/%(member_id)s/%(table_id)s/%(variable_id)s/%(grid_label)s/%(version)s
 - index_node = esgf-node.ipsl.upmc.fr

- number_of_aggregations = 2
- number_of_files = 1
- size = 475508
- Coverage
 - datetime_start = 2000-04-16T00:00:00Z
 - datetime_stop = 2001-05-16T12:00:00Z
 - east_degrees = 357.5
 - north_degrees = 90.0
 - south_degrees = -90.0
 - west_degrees = 0.0
 - geos = ENVELOPE(-180.0, -2.5, 90.0, -90.0), ENVELOPE(0.0, 180.0, 90.0, -90.0)
 - geo_units = degrees_east

3.2.11 The ADAM platform

Several activities have been funded by the European Space Agency and the European Commission to demonstrate the full potential of Data Cube technology to access a large variety of EO data and products (Level 1 to Level 4, Low to High / Very High spatial resolution, gridded data, swath data, etc.) as well as the feasibility of direct exploitation of EO data products available in cloud environments (DIAS, Amazon Web Services, private cloud) and in the ESA dissemination services.

The Advanced geospatial Data Management (ADAM) platform (<https://adamplatform.eu/>) is adopted by the European Space Agency to enable pixel-based services on top of ESA Earth Explorer, Heritage Mission and Third-Party Mission datasets. This platform provides Data Cube discovery and access services for a large variety and volume of global environmental data.

The ADAM Explorer provides discovery, access, visualization and processing services on top of the 3D virtual globe powered by ESA-NASA Web World Wind, as follows:

- Data discovery. Datasets can be identified either by type of application (e.g., agriculture, atmosphere, climate, cultural heritage, etc.) or by type of sensor (e.g., Copernicus C3S, ESA-CCI, GPM IMERG, Landsat-8, etc.). And for each of these ones, the temporal and spatial coverage can be selected.
- Data access and exploration. The selected data can be loaded into the system, as shown in the figure (where the sea temperature in a region is visualized).
- Data processing. Basic processing functions are provided (e.g. accumulated / averaged values over a selected area of interest for a defined timeframe, correlations between two datasets, etc.).

For this specific platform, all operations can be done without downloading the data locally, optimizing data access and multi-dimensional sub-setting. The figure above shows a series of snapshots of the ADAM Explorer displaying NO2 from Copernicus Sentinel-5P from global, to European, to country-level, including the time evolution over two points in the city of Vienna during the COVID-19 period.

All these services are provided using existing standards from the Open Geospatial Consortium: OGC OpenSearch, Web Map Tile Service (WMTS) and Web Coverage Service (WCS). Besides, it is important to note the distinction that is being done in this platform between products and datasets. In ADAM, a **product** refers to the single resource indexed in the Data Cube (e.g., each single satellite image), while **datasets** are series of products with a common meaning. For satellite data this usually refers to a thematic product or parameter/field/variable (e.g., the "Sentinel-5P Aerosol Index Near Real Time"), and there is some flexibility on its definition: the Sentinel-5P Aerosol Index may include all products from NRTI, OFFL and RPRO processing streams.

Given a dataset, the following attributes are currently made available:

- General properties, such as dataset identifier, creation and update dates, number of records.

-
- Measurement properties, such as the datatype used for observations, the unit, the minimum value (with its corresponding time instant) and the maximum value (with its corresponding time instant), the numeric value used when no data is available.
 - Temporal coverage, including the temporal resolution
 - Spatial information, including the geometry, the coordinate reference system, the resolution and the resolution unit, the scale factor.
 - Keywords related to the types of applications for the dataset.
 - Licensing information, and pricing information
 - Provenance information, including the processing stream (currently satellite, numerical forecast, planetary space data and point cloud), and each of them with their own metadata schema. For instance, for satellite data, the following attributes are provided: name, mission, sensor, processing level, instrument, platform, and product type.
 - Data management information, including the dataset manager and organization, the technical manager, and the data access endpoint.

For a specific product, the reference to the dataset identifier is provided, as well as details on the specific product (product identifier, date, geometry and path where it can be found). The rest of information is taken from the dataset.

3.2.12 OGC OpenSearch Earth Observation systems

OGC OpenSearch Earth Observation systems follow the OGC OpenSearch Earth Observation extension¹¹. This extension distinguishes between Earth Observation Collections and Products (EO Collection and EO Product, respectively), and identifies the corresponding metadata for each of them. This is reflected in the UML model of the following figure, and described in detail, together with the corresponding mappings and crosswalks with respect to other metadata models, at the document referenced above. It is especially relevant to point out that Annex D in that document provides several mappings between this metadata schema and other metadata profiles and schemas that are also used in this context, such as the EO Metadata profile of Observations and Measurements (OGC 10-157r4)¹², the ISO 19115 / ISO 19115-2 Geographic Information Metadata, and the OGC CS Extension Package for ebRIM (ebXML Registry Information Model) Application Profiles (EO Products¹³, I15¹⁴, SensorML¹⁵).

¹¹ OGC 13-026r8, OGC OpenSearch Extension for Earth Observation Products, 2016.

<https://docs.openeospatial.org/is/13-026r8/13-026r8.html>

¹² OGC 10-157r4, Earth Observation Metadata profile of Observations & Measurements, Version 1.1, 2016.

<http://docs.openeospatial.org/is/10-157r4/10-157r4.html>

¹³ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/cat2eoext4ebrim>

¹⁴ <https://www.ogc.org/projects/groups/i15swg>

¹⁵ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/sensorml>

Datasets (EO collections) can be searched for using the following parameters:

- productType
- doi
- platform
- platformSerialIdentifier
- instrument
- sensorType
- compositeType
- processingLevel
- orbitType
- spectralRange
- wavelength
- hasSecurityConstraints
- dissemination
- sru:recordSchema, which allows pointing to any other additional metadata (ISO19115, OGC O&M, SensorML, Dublin Core, etc.).

In the case of specific EO products, which are part of EO Collections, the following parameters can be used:

- parentIdentifier
- productionStatus (e.g., ARCHIVED, ACQUIRED, CANCELLED)
- acquisitionType (e.g., NOMINAL, CALIBRATION, OTHER)
- Orbit details: orbitNumber, orbitDirection, track and frame
- swathIdentifier (e.g., Envisat ASAR I1, I2, etc.)
- cloudCover and snowCover
- lowestLocation and highestLocation
- productVersion
- productQualityStatus (e.g., NOMINAL, DEGRADED)
- productQualityDegradationTag
- processorName
- processingCenter (e.g. PDHS-E, PDHS-K, DPA, F-ACRI) and archivingCenter
- creationDate, modificationDate, processingDate

- sensorMode
- processingMode (e.g., real time, near real time, etc.)

Finally, there are also some options to perform searches based on acquisition parameters, which are not detailed further in this document as they are not relevant for the purpose of this analysis.

Based on this metadata model, there is a recent GeoJSON(-LD) encoding format that can be used for the representation of OGC EO Dataset Metadata¹⁶, which serves as an inspiration for the model that we are proposing in Section 5 of this document. Unfortunately, the ontology that is described in that document is not publicly available online, although the corresponding OWL code is included in the document. The main groups of properties that can be associated to any EO collection or product, and their identifiers, are (in bold those that are compulsory):

- Data identification: **identifier**, **title**, parentIdentifier, **date**, created, available, doi
- Metadata information: updated, published, creationDate, status (ARCHIVED, PLANNED, ACQUIRED, CANCELLED, FAILED, POTENTIAL, REJECTED, QUALITYDEGRADED).
- Geometry: **type**, **id**, **geometry**, **properties**, bbox
- Product information
 - o productType, size, productVersion, statusSubType (ON-LINE, OFF-LINE), statusDetail, **availabilityTime**, timeliness, productGroupId, archivingCenter, referenceSystemIdentifier, archivingDate
 - o *Processing information*: processingLevel (1A,1B,1C,2,3), processorName, processorVersion, processingCenter, processingDate, processingMode, compositeType, format, productContentsType, processingMethod, processingMethodVersion
 - o *Quality information*: qualityStatus (NORMAL, DEGRADED), qualityDegradation, qualityDegradationTag, qualityDegradationQuotationMode.
 - o *Coverage description*: cloudCover, snowCover
- Acquisition information
 - o *Instrument*: id, sensorType (OPTICAL, RADAR, ATMOSPHERIC, ALTIMETRIC, LIMB), **instrumentShortName**, description
 - o *Platform*: id, **platformShortName**, platformSerialIdentifier, orbitType (GEO, LEO)
 - o *Acquisition parameters* (wavelength information, acquisition angles, orbit parameters, temporal information, vertical spatial domain): **acquisitionType** (NOMINAL, CALIBRATION, OTHER), acquisitionSubType, startTimeFromAscendingNode, completionTimeFromAscendingNode, relativeOrbitNumber, wrsLongitude, wrsLatitude, tileId, groundTrackingUncertainty, cycleNumber, antennaLookDirection, acquisitionStation, acquisitionAngles, operationalMode, swathIdentifier, polarisationMode, polarisationChannels, resolution, verticalResolution, waveLengths, measurementType (ABSORPTION, EMISSION), dopplerFrequency, samplingRates.
 - *Wavelength information*: type, discreteWavelengths, endWavelengths, spectralRange (INFRARED, NIR, SWIR, MWIR, LWIR, FIR, UV,

¹⁶ OGC 17-003r2, OGC EO Dataset Metadata GeoJSON(-LD) Encoding Standard, 2020.
<https://docs.openeospatial.org/is/17-003r2/17-003r2.html>

Given the fact that extensions are allowed, for specific types of products new properties can be included. As an example, for the Electro-Optical Extension we can find `eo:bands` and `eo:cloud_cover` as properties that can be added, where bands are describe by their name, common name, description, center wavelength and full width half max (FWHM). More specifically, and of interest for RELIANCE, is the DataCube extension (<https://github.com/stac-extensions/datacube>), which defines dimensions that can be spatial, temporal, vertical or any other, and which allow defining the type of dimension, description, extent, values, steps and reference system, with small differences among different types of dimensions.

3.3 Reusable semantic artefacts (metadata models, controlled vocabularies)

The analysis of resource (and data) catalogues presented in the previous section has shown that there a number of semantic artefacts that may be used for the purpose of describing and searching for data cubes (including collections/datasets and products).

This section focuses on identifying, enumerating and briefly describing these semantic artefacts, which are mostly metadata schemes and lightweight vocabularies. It also refers to those controlled vocabularies and code lists that can be used by different user communities to describe parameters, variables, experiments, geographical areas, expeditions, cruises, etc. As with the descriptions provided in the previous section, this list should not be considered exhaustive, since we have acquired them through interviews with a selected set of researchers from the communities that RELIANCE focuses on. The main objective is to identify those semantic artefacts that may be included and referenced to in a single portal in RELIANCE to allow for the description of the data cubes used by the communities of researchers.

It is also important to note that we are not focusing on semantic artefacts that would allow describing specific data records or data points (even though this will be possible in some cases, as shown, for example, in the case of ADAM) and would allow for further interoperability of data. We keep our descriptions at the level of dataset/collection/product description.

The following set of semantic artefacts have been considered. Crosswalks across them (and associated sometimes with the systems used for dataset search) are provided in annex I, and as part of the accompanying documentation available in Zenodo (Corcho, González-Guardia and Garijo, 2021). Following state of the art practices in many EOSC-related initiatives, these crosswalks are provided in Excel format, and may be enabled in the future in the context of the RELIANCE platform.

3.3.1 General purpose dataset/product-description metadata models

The following general purpose metadata models have been identified as relevant, and will be partially supported by RELIANCE as needed:

- The OpenAIRE metadata model described in the OpenAIRE metadata guidelines for data archives.
- The ISO 19115 content model (used, for example, by NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information services).

- The ISO 19139 content model (used, for example, by the SeaDataNet Cruise Summary Report – CSR¹⁹ - and Common Data Index - CDI²⁰ - services), which extends the previous one for INSPIRE-compliance.
- The schema.org/DataSet format (used, for example, by PANGAEA).
- NetCDF
- OGC OpenSearch Extension for Earth Observation
- OGC EO Dataset Metadata GeoJSON(-LD) Encoding, with its corresponding ontology (available as two files, not published following good ontology publishing practices, at <http://schemas.opengis.net/eo-geojson/1.0/eo-geojson-vocabulary.owl> and <http://schemas.opengis.net/eo-geojson/1.0/owc-geojson-vocabulary.owl>).

Besides, the catalogue of metadata standards maintained by RDA at <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/scheme-index> will be continuously monitored throughout the execution of the project so as to keep an eye on the developments of different metadata standards, and their cross-mappings.

3.3.2 *Earth-Observation-related semantic artefacts*

In this group we include those semantic artefacts that are specifically allowing the representation of data related to Earth Observation. We include here those related to Copernicus missions as well as the SWEET ontology.

- Metadata models for Copernicus missions: <https://spacedata.copernicus.eu/data-offer/inspire-compliant-metadata>
- The Semantic Web for Earth and Environment Technology (SWEET) ontology (<https://github.com/ESIPFed/sweet>) is governed by the ESIP Semantic Technologies Committee, and is focused on the representation of many different types of concepts related to physical quantities, Earth realms, space, time, etc.). Many of the ontologies in this suite of ontologies may be useful for the representation of aspects related to our domains (e.g., types of volcanoes at <http://sweetontology.net/realmlandvolcanic>).

3.3.3 *Domain-specific semantic artefacts*

For each of the domains that are covered in the context of RELIANCE, we have also identified, via interviews and analysis of available documentation and references done from the data access systems described in section 2, the following semantic artefacts:

- The SeaDataNet Common Vocabularies: <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Common-Vocabularies> (as referenced from <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats>). This includes: EDMED (European Directory of Marine Environmental Data)²¹, EDMERP (European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Projects)²², or EDIOS (European Directory of the Ocean Observing Systems)²³, among others.
- The SeaBASS oceanographic and atmospheric in-situ measurements vocabulary: <https://seabass.gsfc.nasa.gov/wiki/metadataheaders>

¹⁹ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/CSR>

²⁰ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/CDI>

²¹ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/EDMED>

²² <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/EDMERP>

²³ <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Metadata-formats/EDIOS>

- Metadata associated to products related to radar data (e.g., SAR Data products developed by EPOS in the Thematic Core Service “Satellite Data” and cured mainly by IREA) for:
 - o LOS_displacement time series
 - o Unwrapped interferograms
 - o Wrapped interferograms
- The NetCDF CF (Climate and Forecast) Conventions: <https://cfconventions.org/>. These are conventions designed to promote the processing and sharing of files created with the NetCDF API.

3.4 Discarded semantic artefacts

Several other semantic artefacts may have been identified as relevant for the purpose of representing data cubes, but are explicitly discarded from our analysis because of the reasons presented below:

- The W3C RDF Data Cube vocabulary (<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-data-cube/>) may seem to be a good fit for the representation of the data cubes that we deal with in RELIANCE. However, the concept of datacube in this context refers to multidimensional data commonly used in the context of statistics, and hence it is not relevant for the types of data cubes that we consider in RELIANCE.
- The W3C Semantic Sensor Network ontology (<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>) is focused on the representation of sensors and their observations. Indeed, it is clear that this ontology would be useful for the representation of the data contained in the datasets and products related to Earth Observation and in-situ observations. However, the focus of this ontology is on the representation of the fine-grained data that is contained in these datasets and products. However, as already described above, we are not interested in such fine-grained representation in the context of RELIANCE.

Obviously, this list is not exhaustive, and only contains these two semantic artefacts that may be initially considered as relevant for this domain in case that somebody is doing a quick search over available artefacts.

4 Requirements. Competency questions

In this section we include the list of competency questions that has been gathered collectively by the user communities in our project. These competency questions have been fundamental in determining which parts of the metadata models that have been presented in section 3.3, and which are core to some of the data search systems presented in section 3.2, are relevant to be included in our proposed Data Cube metadata model.

The process of collecting competency questions is common in most ontology development methodologies, and particularly in the Linked Open Terms methodology (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2019), which is the one that has been used for the purpose of deriving our Data Cube metadata model. Particularly, in our case these competency questions have been also used for the evaluation of the generated metadata model, with each of them having been transformed into their corresponding SPARQL queries, which will be used in the future when the metadata of our data cubes are made available via the RELIANCE Data-Cube related services.

Competency question	Domains
Which are the datasets that have been produced or collected in project X? (e.g., Which are the datasets collected during the SNAPSHOT project?)	General

Is there any available time series of images from Satellite-X over a particular region of the globe?	General
Which are the datasets about KD490 that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 2002 and 2018?	Marine
Which are the datasets about KD490 that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 2002 and 2018 at 0 and 300 meters water depth?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Chl-a that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 2002 and 2018?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Sea Surface Temperature that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1955 and 2017?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Sea Surface Temperature that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Temperature that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1955 and 2017 at 200 m?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Salinity that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1955 and 2017?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Salinity that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Nutrients (Nitrate) that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Nutrients (Phosphate) that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which are the datasets about Dissolved Oxygen that cover the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which is the water depth of the 14 degree isotherm in the Mediterranean Sea in the period between 1999 and 2021?	Marine
Which are the datasets about VARIABLE X that cover Sea X in the period between DD/MM/YYYY and DD/MM/YYYY at XX water depth?	Marine
What data can I use to estimate the change in area, length and elevation of glacier XY between YYYY-MM-DD-1 and YYYY-MM-DD-2?	Climate
Which are the datasets containing the mass balance of glacier XY in YYYY?	Climate
Which are the datasets containing the mass balance of glacier XY in YYYY or between YYYY-1 and YYYY-2? Is it positive or negative?	Climate
Which dataset has the longest mass balance time series for glacier XY? When was the start date?	Climate
Which are the datasets containing the snow cover duration in Region X and period YYYY-MM-DD-1 to YYYY-MM-DD-2?	Climate
Which dataset can I use to assess the snow-melt season start in region X in YYYY?	Climate
Is there a consistent pattern in mass balance change for all glaciers in country XY / region XY in the period YYYY-1 to YYYY-2?	Climate
Is the yearly mass balance change related to changes in temperature or precipitation?	Climate
Are there satellite images showing the end of summer snowline in YYYY?	Climate
Are there satellite images showing the distribution of glacier facies (snow,firm,ice) on YYYY-MM-DD?	Climate

Are timeseries with sufficient spatial resolution available to identify urbanized areas versus agricultural or natural areas to identify areas where urban areas have significantly increased at the expense of agricultural or natural areas?	Climate
Is there any data available to identify the change of vegetation/trees (from birch to coniferous, for example) observed at northern latitudes? are these changes identifiable by satellite? has the boundary moved north?	Climate
Which dataset are used to assess the vegetation on earth?	Climate
Which are the datasets showing deforestation in South America (or Madagascar) and land cover changes since YYYY?	Climate
Which are the datasets for snow cover over Norway?	Climate
Is there any available dataset for snow cover since 1970 for Norway?	Climate
Which are the datasets for ice cover in Greenland since YYYY?	Climate
Is there a time series showing the area of a particular lake L derived from satellite images (to see if it is drying out)?	Climate
Is there any information about vegetation derived from satellite imagery (NDVI, LAI, etc.) in the area used by reindeer husbandry (northern Norway/Sweden/Finland) covering the last 40 years	Climate
Which are the datasets for vegetation cover in the arctic since 1980?	Climate
Which datasets can be used to study land-use changes in a particular country or region over the last 40 years or so?	Climate
Which datasets are able to provide information about cloud coverage so that I can compute the % contrail area visible on satellite images and see the lockdown affected aerial transports since 2020?	Climate
What climate prediction is available for a particular region of the globe (Europe, Australia, etc.)?	Climate
What climate data is available - could be 2m air temperature, precipitation, etc. - over which period (pre-industrial, present day, future scenarios, etc.) - is it from measurements? numerical modelling?	Climate
Are there satellite images allowing to see the plume after the eruption of volcano V which occurred on YYYY-MM-DD at a particular location on Earth?	Vulcanology

5 Our proposed model

In this section we describe the proposed metadata model that results from the analysis presented in the previous sections as well as from the recommendations on metadata descriptions for FAIR Digital Objects proposed by the EOSC Interoperability Framework (Corcho et al., 2021). As discussed in this document, several metadata layers can be associated to a single digital object (which may be a dataset or collection, or a product generated statically or dynamically, as discussed in section 3). In our proposal, we consider the following four main layers:

- **General metadata layer**, which allows representing general information about the digital object (data cube) and is aligned with the recommendations proposed by OpenAIRE (OpenAIRE metadata guidelines for Data Providers), and hence aligned with DataCite. The objective of this layer is to allow for these digital objects to be easily ingested in the

OpenAIRE Research Graph. The properties proposed for this layer are the following (in bold font those that are compulsory)²⁴:

- **Identifier** (identifier)
- Alternate identifier (alternateIdentifiers/alternateIdentifier)
- Related identifier (relatedIdentifiers/relatedIdentifier)
- **Title** (title)
- **ResourceType** (resourceType equal to Dataset, for the time being, although we will aim at generating a DataCube resource type in the future)
- **Publication year** (publicationYear)
- Description (descriptions/description)
- Creation date (dct:created, dates/date [dateType=])
- Modification date (dct:modified)
- Publication date (dct:date)
- Version (version)
- Update frequency (dct:accrualPeriodicity)
- Purpose (subjects/subject, with free keywords)
- ParentIdentifier/inCollection (eop:parentIdentifier)
- Status (eop:status)
- Language (language)
- Related Items (relatedItems/relatedItem)
- **Credit, licensing and pricing layer**, which is also aligned as much as possible with the recommendations from OpenAIRE, and is also data cube and domain independent.
 - **Authors** (creators/creator)
 - Contributors (contributors/contributor)
 - **Publisher** (publisher)
 - Rights List (rightsList/rights)
 - Funding References (fundingReferences/fundingReference)
- **Coverage metadata layer**, which allows representing those aspects related to the spatial and temporal coverage of the data cube, which are essential when looking for data cubes across all domains.
 - Simple GeoLocation, for simple tools like CKAN and alike (according to DataCite, including geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPlace, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPoint, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationBox, geoLocations/geolocation/geoLocationPolygon)
 - **Spatial coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, coordinate reference system).
 - **Temporal coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit).
 - Vertical coverage, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit).
 - No other dimensions are foreseen yet, although new use cases may bring additional dimensions.
- **Data Acquisition and Product Information layer**, which allows representing those aspects related to the observations, processing levels, instruments, platforms, missions, etc. In general, for this metadata layer we will allow for the usage of general keywords (user-

²⁴ All the attributes presented in parenthesis in this general metadata layer belong to the DataCite metadata schema (<http://schema.datacite.org/>). Details on the usage of some of these properties can be also found, for the general metadata layer, at <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/>

defined or associated to controlled lists) in the keywords section, so as to facilitate usage across domains.

- **Keywords**
- **Product type**
- Product version
- Data type
- Data type unit
- Size (sizes/size)
- Format (formats/format)
- Processing level
- Processor
- Instrument
- Platform
- Other Data Acquisition System
- Data Quality
- maxValue
- minValue
- maxDate
- minDate
- noDataValue
- Links to resources
- Point of Contact

6 Annex I. Crosswalks among metadata models

As discussed in several parts of this document, an Excel file with the crosswalks among metadata models has been made available in Zenodo as part of this deliverable.

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